

И. Н. Жуков, – педагог, который назвал советских детей пионерами

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Актуальность статьи определяется стремлением к поиску новаторских методов работы, способных соответствовать требованиям нашего времени и запросам участников современного образовательного процесса в школе. *Цель статьи* заключается в обращении к практическому педагогическому опыту Иннокентия Николаевича Жукова, который ярко проявил себя как организатор скаутского и пионерского движения, автор идеи длительной воспитательной игры, детский писатель и скульптор.

Материалы и методы. В качестве методов исследования автор использовал анализ историко-педагогической литературы, биографический и мемуарный, а также ценностный (аксиологический), формационный и региональный научно-методологические подходы.

Результаты. Видный советский педагог первой половины XX века И. Н. Жуков (1875-1948) выступил в качестве одного из первых пропагандистов и организаторов скаутской организации в досоветской России. Он принял активное участие в организации пионерского движения, и даже предложил само слово «пионер». Был автором значительного числа публикаций по вопросам воспитания детей и подростков, а также полезных, увлекательных книг для юношества.

Обсуждение. Видные деятели культуры и педагогики, в том числе О. Роден, Н. К. Крупская, Л. Н. Толстой, А. М. Горький, А. В. Луначарский, С. Т. Коненков и другие, высоко оценивали вклад И. Н. Жукова в отечественное образование и искусство как педагога, скульптора и детского писателя. В указанных сферах И. Н. Жуков проявил себя как новатор, стремившийся к активизации интереса детей посредством использования игрового метода.

Заключение. Плодотворная, многогранная деятельность педагога, писателя и скульптора И. Н. Жукова представляет собой яркое явление в истории отечественного образования первой половины XX в. Игровой подход к воспитанию и обучению детей нашел плодотворное развитие в трудах следующих поколений отечественных педагогов и, несомненно, заслуживает дальнейшего изучения в интересах современной теории и практики образования.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

скаутизм, пионерское движение, длительная воспитательная игра, Наркомпрос РСФСР, Жуков, Луначарский, Крупская, Роден, ваяние

Для цитирования: Помелов В. Б. И. Н. Жуков, – педагог, который назвал советских детей пионерами // Перспективы науки и образования. 2025. № 1. С. 595–605. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2025.1.38>

Поступила: 17.08.2024 | Одобрена: 12.11.2024 | Опубликована: 28.02.2025

Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

I. N. Zhukov, a teacher who called soviet children pioneers

V. B. POMELOV

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of the article is determined by the desire to search for innovative working methods that can meet the requirements of our time and meet the needs of participants in the modern educational process at school. The purpose of the article is to refer to the practical pedagogical experience of a prominent Soviet teacher of the first half of the XX century. Innokenty Nikolaevich Zhukov (1875-1948), who vividly proved himself as an organizer of the scout and pioneer movement, the author of the idea of a long educational game, a children's writer and sculptor.

Materials and methods. The author used the analysis of historical and pedagogical literature, biographical and memoir research methods, as well as value (axiological), formational and regional scientific and methodological approaches.

Results. I. N. Zhukov acted as one of the first propagandists and organizers of the scout organization in pre-Soviet Russia. He took an active part in the organization of the pioneer movement, and even suggested the very word "pioneer". He was the author of a significant number of publications on the education of children and adolescents, as well as useful, fascinating books for young people. He showed himself vividly as a sculptor.

Discussion. Prominent figures of culture and pedagogy, including O. Rodin, N. K. Krupskaya, L. N. Tolstoy, A.M. Gorky, A.V. Lunacharsky, S. T. Konenkov and others, highly appreciated I. N. Zhukov's contribution to Russian education and art as a teacher, sculptor and children's writer. In these areas, I. N. Zhukov proved himself to be an innovator who sought to activate the interest of children through the use of the game method.

Conclusion. The fruitful, multifaceted activity of the teacher, writer and sculptor I. N. Zhukov is a vivid phenomenon in the history of Russian education in the first half of the XX century. The playful approach to the upbringing and education of children has found fruitful development in the works of the next generations of Russian teachers and undoubtedly deserves further study in the interests of modern theory and practice of education.

KEYWORDS

scouting, pioneer movement, long-term educational game, People's Commissariat of the RSFSR, Zhukov, Lunacharsky, Krupskaya, Rodin, sculpting

For Citation: Pomelov, V. B. (2025). I. N. Zhukov, a teacher who called soviet children pioneers. *Perspektivy nauki i obrazovaniya = Perspectives of Science and Education*, (1), 595–605. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2025.1.38>

Received: 17 August 2024 | Approved: 12 November 2024 | Published: 28 February 2025

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INTRODUCTION

Currently, in modern pedagogical thought and educational practice, especially important importance is attached to the personality of a teacher who is able to contribute to solving the most difficult pedagogical tasks by his example, activity and ingenuity. In this regard, historical and pedagogical thought, first of all, refers to the experience of the glorious representatives of pedagogical science and practice of the past years [1]. Pedagogical journals publish articles characterizing the best representatives of different eras, countries and generations, starting from the time of the enlighteners of their people [2], the peoples of other countries and the founders of the first didactically correctly organized educational institutions [3]. As before, in the works of historians of pedagogy, special attention is paid to the study of the legacy of generally recognized luminaries of education, such as J. G. Pestalozzi [4], J. F. Herbart [5], F. Froebel [6] and D. Dewey [7].

But no matter how valuable the search for axiological content in the legacy of teachers of long-past eras [8], including religious leaders of their time, who clearly manifested themselves in pedagogical work [9], researchers still pay the main attention to revealing the valuable contribution of teachers closer to modern times, i.e. outstanding teachers [10] and the organizers of education of the XX century [11]. Some modern researchers even predict the possibility of introducing artificial intelligence into the educational process [12], and it is on a game basis at that [13]. This idea is becoming more widespread in Eastern European countries [14].

Such views are quite in line with the views of the remarkable Russian teacher I. N. Zhukov. The name of Innokenty Nikolaevich Zhukov has never been under a public or tacit ban, but despite this, Soviet historians of education invariably "bypassed" him in their writings.

This is explained by the fact that completely different teachers were "identified" in the USSR by generally recognized authorities on the establishment and organization of the pioneer movement in the 1920s and 1930s. In the article presented to the reader, the author sought to comprehensively show the personality of the remarkable Russian teacher of the first half of the XX century, to reveal the content of his many years of efforts in the field of organizing the children's movement, to assess some areas of his multifaceted activities. This seems especially relevant in the year of the 150th anniversary of his birth.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The author actively used an axiological research approach, which allows to identify the value content in the work of the studied historical personality. Due to the fact that I. N. Zhukov's activities were carried out during a crucial historical period for the Russian state, the author partially applied formational and regional approaches. The research methods used include biographical and memoir, as well as the method of working with literature.

The author used in his article the works of such researchers as H. F. Rupp, P. Peña Búa, K. D. Malafantis, A. Németh, B. Pukánszky, P. Kimourtzis, I. Betsas, R. Bruno, C. Martínez, B. Comella-Gutierrez, J. L. Rodríguez-Sáez, L. J. Martín-Antón, M. Á. Carbonero-Martín, J. Meda, M. Ostenc, G. Nistor, A. Iacob, S. Stoyanov, T. Glushkova, V. Tabakova-Komsalova, V. Ivanova, A. Stoyanova-Doycheva, A. Petrov, B. Dokthaisong, etc.

Their works have been published in the following journals: UNESCO. Oficina Internacional de Educación, Perspectives of Science and Education, History of Education & Children's Literature, Publicaciones de la Universidad de Salamanca, Encuentros sobre Educación, Espacio, Tiempo y Educación, eLearning&Software for Education, The Educational Review, USA, International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research.

RESULTS

A prominent Russian teacher, one of the organizers of the scout and pioneer movement in our country, the famous sculptor and children's writer Innokenty Nikolaevich Zhukov was born on October 5 (17), 1875, in the village of Gorny Zerentuy, district of the Nerchinsky plant, now a village in the Nerchinsk-Zavodsky district of the Trans-Baikal Territory, in the family of the titular adviser, the manager of the Gorno-Zerentuysky mine Nikolai Mikhailovich Zhukov and Agrippina (Agrophenes) Afanasyevna (nee Savinskaya). Innokenty was the fifth child in the family, and there were eight of them in total [15, p. 342].

In 1895, Zhukov entered the Literature department of the Historical and Philological Faculty of the Imperial St. Petersburg University. In 1899, he was expelled from the university for participating in the All-Russian student strike. In 1901, he managed to recover at the University. In the spring of 1902, he passed the state exam and finally received a diploma. He loved geography and teaching this academic subject became his profession. He started as a teacher in private schools in the capital (1902-1912).

In the last years of his University life, the young man also became seriously interested in art. He was actively engaged in modeling and drawing in the sculpture class of the rector of the Higher Art School at the Imperial Academy of Arts V. A. Beklemishev. The level of I. N. Zhukov's work was such that, starting in 1906, he took part in the annual autumn exhibitions in St. Petersburg, which were organized by the patron P. D. Prokofiev. For seven years, Zhukov participated in a total of nine exhibitions, where he demonstrated over six hundred of his works. He had a good press, – about a hundred publications and responses. Approximately 150,000 photo postcards with images of his sculptors have been distributed in Russia and abroad.

Friends helped him get a scholarship from the Academy of Fine Arts, and in 1912 Innokenty went to Paris, where he hoped to improve his skills. A long-awaited meeting took place with Auguste Rodin (1840-1917), whom, even before his arrival, he asked in a letter to become his mentor.

However, after reviewing the photographic images of Zhukov's works, the world-famous sculptor refused to cooperate with the Russian sculptor, citing his advanced age, as well as the fact that Innokenty, in his opinion, had already established himself as a master.

According to I. N. Zhukov, O. Rodin ended his letter with the words: "You have too much personality, and you would waste a lot of time fighting with another individual. Let nature itself be your master" [16]. I. N. Zhukov began studying in the studio of sculptor Emile Antoine Bourdelle (1861-1929), a pupil of Rodin, and in the same group with V. I. Mukhina.

In 1914, Zhukov began teaching geography at the St. Petersburg orphan Institute, continued sculpting, and also actively joined in the development of a new business for himself, the creation of a scout organization. He became interested in the ideas of the remarkable Canadian naturalist writer Ernest Evan Seton-Thompson (1860-1946), who later became the first leader of the Boy Scouts of North America. In his estate near New York, he organized an "Indian village" for local boys, and practiced working with them for long games on the ground with tracking down the enemy, chasing, reading tracks, etc.

An important source of information on the scout movement for Zhukov were the books of the founder of scouting, retired British Colonel Robert Baden-Powell (1857-1941) "To help scouts" (1901) and "Scouting for boys" (1908). They focused on military sports training of the younger generation, and, above all, on such forms of training for young men as operational military intelligence, reading military maps, physical training, overcoming obstacles, the life of teenagers outside civilization, in natural conditions, etc. [17, p. 13].

The first groups of Russian scouts appeared in Tsarskoye Selo, St. Petersburg, Moscow, and Batumi in 1908-1911. The idea of creating patriotic children's organizations was supported by the Russian Emperor Nicholas II himself. By his order, the General Staff translated and published in Russia in 1910 the book "Scouting for boys" under a slightly different title "Young Scout. The Guide to Scouting" [18, p. 81]. The emblem of the Russian scouts was a white lily, and the motto consisted of the call "Be ready!" and the answer "Always ready! For Russia!"

In 1914, the All-Russian Society for the Assistance of Scout Boys "Russian Scout" was founded in Petrograd, headed by its chairman, Admiral Ivan Fedorovich Bostrom, and patroness, Grand Duchess Elizabeth Fedorovna, sister of the Empress. I. N. Zhukov became secretary of this society. In 1916, he received the honorary title of "senior friend of the scouts of Russia" [19, p. 4].

By 1917, an organized network of scout associations had developed in Russia. In the summers of 1914 and 1915, near Petrograd, in the village of Popovka, now the village of Krasny Bor in the Tosnensky district of the Leningrad region, Zhukov led a scout troop. His sculpture workshop, which was housed in a large, sturdy barn, served at the same time as the headquarters of a detachment of young scouts.

Classes were held here three times a week, during which conversations about the laws and commandments of the scouts alternated with specific, practical tasks, such as building a fence for a school, organizing a concert for the local population, uprooting stumps, playing a competition, hiking on the Izhora River, spending the night in tents, etc. Teacher A. V. Vakhtin recalled that the scout children were trained in shooting and hand-to-hand combat.

Thus, a kind of initial military training was carried out. With the older boys from Popovka, I. N. Zhukov created a voluntary youth fire society. His daughter, Irina Innokentievna Zhukova-Plotnikova, recalled that children from all over the village came running to them. Innokenty Nikolaevich organized a theater in the courtyard, held sports competitions.

The historian of the children's movement V. G. Yakovlev, in his memoirs "Our Uncle Keshka", written for the 90th anniversary of Zhukov's birth, wrote: "I still remember how 50 years ago, we boys and girls loved to run to our beloved "Uncle Keshka". He was a geography teacher, but in his spare time he sculpted and was fond of playing games with the guys...".

In December 1915, Zhukov made a report "The goals and objectives of Scouting in Russia" at the 1st All-Russian Congress of Instructors and Persons interested in Scouting. The Congress approved materials that were mandatory in the work of scout groups, including the scout prayer and the scout laws, which were formulated by Zhukov.

In September 1917, Zhukov and his family left for Chita. There he lectured at school leadership training courses, organized scout holidays, taught classes at the faculty, organized "Child Weeks", held summer camps, and wrote several plays for school theaters. He promoted his pedagogical ideas, led discussions on the pages of the socio-pedagogical newspaper "Thoughts of the Trans-Baikal Teacher" and the journal "Bulletin of Enlightenment".

A major obstacle in the development of the scout movement was the chronic lack of literature. Therefore, in 1921 Zhukov published in Chita the brochures "Satellite of the Siberian scout", "The program of scouting classes. A guide for scoutmasters", as well as a book revealing the methodology of conducting long-term educational games called "Packs of cubs and chicks". Under his leadership, journals began to be published in Chita, - "Zabaikalsky scout" and "Zabaikalsky boy scout".

Articles by scoutmasters on work practices, a chronicle of the scout movement in Siberia, materials to help scouts and tips for beginners, a review of literature for children and adolescents were published here. I. N. Zhukov explained the success of spreading the idea and practice of scouting by the fact that this system of children's activities fully took into account the psychological and pedagogical nature of child development, and had basically a long-term educational game. He considered such a game to be a very valuable acquisition of pedagogy, and urged teachers to put the idea of such games into the practice of extracurricular education.

In 1918, he developed the idea of a long-term game, called the "Trans-Baikal Expeditionary Corps" [20]. Having gathered about 700 children aged 10-14 years, he invited them to go through all of Transbaikalia in the summer in order to study its geography, flora and fauna. Zhukov announced the creation of an "expeditionary force." The children were divided by "specialties" into detachments of scouts, cooks, orderlies, hunters, fishermen, botanists, zoologists, chroniclers, photographers, etc. In order to prepare for a long journey, "Uncle Keshka" offered the children a whole test program.

He organized hikes and excursions around the city, during which collections of minerals and plants were collected, and group competitions were organized. This kind of competition continued after the completion of the excursions while processing the collected material. It consisted in independently finding and identifying ten Transbaikalian plants, insects, birds, animals, fish, etc.

As a result, children began to study more, read more, and be interested in the nature and history of the region. In addition, it was announced that hooligans and smokers wouldn't be taken on the trip. As a result, discipline in educational institutions has increased.

Thus, Zhukov's scouts weren't only scouts, but also researchers, local history tourists. He was preparing to conduct a "great journey through the Trans-Baikal region." However, as the detachments of the White Guard ataman G. M. Semenov approached Chita, Zhukov was forced to disband his "corps" and cancel the trip. The very idea of the "Expeditionary Corps" became the first pedagogical experience of mass involvement of children in a long-term educational game to explore their native land, but the civil war prevented the completion of this wonderful experience.

Another significant pedagogical experience of Zhukov was the "Potato Competition" organized by him. The Ministry of Public Education of the Far East, by its order, instructed Zhukov to hold the I-st agronomic competition within the Trans-Baikal region. In the spring, ads appeared in Chita in which all school-age children were invited to participate in this competition.

They were asked to form groups of three or more people and grow potatoes on their own in the allocated areas. The winners received a soccer ball and a set of books as prizes. Harvesting must take place in the presence of a school teacher or an employee of any institution where there is a seal. Members of the commission drew up a protocol and sent it to the Ministry. The ad also gave instructions on growing potatoes and recommendations from an agronomist. The competition turned into a major event that captivated children and adults. As a result, the Ministry received more than five hundred reports from collective participants. Thus, the teacher put into practice the fruitful pedagogical methods of long-term role-playing put forward by him.

In 1921, Zhukov wrote an open letter of the "senior friend of the scouts", to all scoutmasters "fighting for a new pedagogy and for new methods of extracurricular education of children of the RSFSR," in which he revealed his understanding of what a Soviet children's organization should be. He encouraged them to set up their pedagogical experiments and conduct educational work in accordance with the system of long-term educational games.

The ascetic work on the organization of the scout movement was carried out by I. N. Zhukov and his volunteer assistants on a voluntary basis in the conditions of the civil war, huge material and everyday difficulties. During the years of the decline of morality, cruelty and permissiveness, they promoted the humanistic, chivalrous nature of the scouts' activities; guided their students to socially useful work, exploring their native land through excursions, hikes and expeditions.

In Moscow, I. N. Zhukov spoke at a meeting in the People's Commissariat of the RSFSR on the organization of a children's movement based on long-term educational play. He urged the heads of Russian education to see scouting, first of all, as a pedagogical system in which the peculiarities of childhood are skillfully used.

In a polemic with N. K. Krupskaya, he urged not to use certain aspects of scouting, but to take it into their own hands entirely, while "clearing historical garbage" [21, p. 17]. His report "On Boy Scouting" was devoted to the same issue at the 33rd meeting of the scientific and pedagogical section of the Main Scientific Council of the People's Commissariat of the RSFSR (Moscow, 1922).

At the same time, he was a categorical opponent of the "politicization" of the children's organization, and official statesmen, on the contrary, strove with all their might to do just that. Zhukov suggested that children of faith should be tolerated, and the Soviet state declared a struggle against religion. He believed that scouting should remain a game for children and adolescents, and "scouting can't and shouldn't aim to draw young souls into any kind of politics with its whirlpool of passions. Politics should be alien to the young, not yet strengthened soul of a schoolboy" [22, p. 42].

He hoped very much that "scouting, freed from bourgeois-political tendencies, can be recognized by the People's Commissariat of Education as a new form of social education" [23, p. 36]. The teacher tried to combine the interests and needs of children and the requests of the state. He called on the pedagogical community for help. He even wrote, apparently more wishful thinking, that "his reports on this topic aroused great interest in pedagogical circles" [23, p. 36].

Meanwhile, the central committee of the Komsomol set a course for the complete elimination of the scout movement. The People's Commissariat of the RSFSR took a more moderate position and tried to attract left-wing scoutmasters to its side in order to create a children's communist organization.

The People's Commissariat of Education, namely N. K. Krupskaya, invited Zhukov, as an experienced scoutmaster, to work on creating a new children's organization. At this crucial time for the children's movement, he, as already noted, went to cooperate with the authorities in creating a new children's organization. Undoubtedly, it was not an easy choice for him. The scout movement in the country still continued to exist. Apparently, anticipating the imminent prohibition of scouting, he didn't want to lose his accumulated experience in scouting, and tried to adapt it to new political conditions. The Scout movement in the USSR was banned in 1923.

In the 1930s, in an atmosphere of unjustified repression, former scouts and scoutmasters, who by that time had become party and Komsomol leaders, were repressed "for helping the international bourgeoisie." Zhukov, together with his friend Valentin Voznesensky, participated in the work of one of the first pioneer detachments, which was organized on the basis of two previously existing "yuk-scout" detachments (yuk – young Communists) (1922). This detachment consisted of students from an experimental school located in the Bauman district of Moscow, and worked at the State Institute of Physical Education (students – future physical education teachers – had practice at this school).

It was Zhukov who proposed the word "pioneers" to designate the participants of the new children's organization, the pioneer motto "Be ready!" and the response cry "Always ready!", as well as the image of a bonfire on the pioneer badge, and the pioneer tie itself in the form of a triangular flap of scarlet cloth.

On March 23, 1923, Zhukov was approved as a member of the Headquarters (Central Bureau) of Young Pioneers, and he was awarded the title of "senior pioneer of the RSFSR". I. N. Zhukov took part in the I-st All-Union Meeting of Pioneers (Moscow, August 1929). He was awarded the title of "People's Teacher".

Zhukov was an opponent of the politicization of the children's movement, and this explains why he gradually moved away from active, direct work in the activities of the pioneer organization. He noted in his diary: "Since 1923, I have moved away from the pioneer movement. In addition, the young Komsomol members who knew me personally treated the employee of the bourgeois scout movement coolly and didn't take the initiative to bring me closer to the unfolding pioneer movement".

I. N. Zhukov was capable of completely unexpected "projects". So, he turned to the People's Commissariat of Education with, as he called it, "a crazy project of an insane person" about the establishment of positions for Robinson Crusoe and his assistant Friday, and he argued for his so unusual proposal by saying that the People's Commissariat of Education was created to work with children and, at the same time, there is no specialist in it to whom children could directly address their needs and requests. It's clear that his proposal, to put it mildly, didn't find understanding in the relevant authorities.

I. N. Zhukov became the author of fascinating children's books written in the genre of fiction, the heroes of which were pioneers. Zhukov's first "pioneer" story "The Journey of the Red Star Link to Wonderland" was first published in the first pioneer journal "Baraban" in 1923-1924 [24].

The story is a kind of communist utopia. A pioneer unit from the city of Lysogorsk went hiking in the forest in the summer of 1923. On the very first evening, settling down for the night at the sawmill, eight boys discovered a strange luminous hatch that takes them back to 1957, – to the

world of the victorious world commune, where the children of the Earth, "all as one", became pioneers. The heroes meet with the pioneers-Leninists of the Eternal Bonfire link, who are called the same as them, only "backwards": a pioneer from 1923, Seryozha Stupin becomes a pioneer from the future named Ahzoyres Niputs. The pioneers of the future talk about the changes that have taken place in the world over 34 years.

In the story "Dead Fire. The adventures of pioneers in Egypt" [25] the author introduces the reader to the distant past of Egypt, the political and economic life of its people, and at the same time, gradually, imperceptibly explains to readers the laws of young pioneers. The stories represented the popularization of the idea of a long-term game, and presented ready-made scenarios for its implementation in practice.

DISCUSSION

Zhukov perceived scouting as a new important means of extracurricular education and upbringing of children. Taking as a basis the book by the founder of the world scout movement R. Baden-Powell, he, in order to familiarize teachers and parents with scouting, at the expense of the Committee for Public Assistance to Scout Boys, published his own version of the manual for scouts called "Russian Scouting. Brief information about the organization of young scouts" (1916) [26].

Following the noble ideas of Seton-Thompson, he wrote that a scout isn't at all a military scout, as Baden-Powell invariably emphasized, but, above all, an altruist, a knight "who is looking for someone to help." He explained the purpose and objectives of the Scout organization in Russia as exclusively knightly, not military. Thus, ideologically, he objected to R. Baden-Powell.

At the same time, I. N. Zhukov borrowed from R. Baden-Powell the ideas of discipline, organization, organizational division of scouts into squads and units, planning work with them, etc. In his book, Innokenty Nikolaevich used the terms "pioneer link" and "squad" long before the appearance of the pioneer organization itself. Zhukov edited the Petrograd Scout journal, which was named as the publication of the First Petrograd Scout Detachment, which was affiliated with the Russian Scout Society (1916).

Thus, from the very beginning of his fascination with the idea of scouting, I. N. Zhukov highlighted in it, first of all, a playful beginning, as well as the opportunity to direct the education of children and adolescents in a direction attractive to every child.

His old friend A. V. Lunacharsky sympathized with him, and he recalled his communication with I. N. Zhukov as follows: "Innokenty Zhukov, having climbed into the depths of Siberia, was, in the literal sense of the word, the initiator of a new, Soviet, red boy scoutism. He brought to this boy scouting not only a revolutionary spirit, but also many of his sweet and, for the most part, talented fantasies... When pioneering began to be built in our country, Innokenty Zhukov was involved in this work and at one time stood close to the very top of the organizers of this business. He was treated with great respect" [27].

Zhukov was a member of the Moscow organization of the Union of Artists of the USSR. He never left sculpting. According to Lunacharsky, he "achieved saturation in the expression of human emotions with clay." His works were located on the territory of the Gorky Central Park of Culture and Recreation, on the square near the Dynamo plant, in the museums of the People's Commissariat of Industry and Osoviakhim, at exhibitions.

Zhukov's works are kept in the Russian Museum (St. Petersburg), the Penza Art Gallery, the art museums of Ivanovo, the Irkutsk Regional Art Museum named after V. P. Sukachev, in the art and local history museums of Chita. Many cultural and educational figures highly appreciated the works of I. N. Zhukov (E. A. Bourdelle, R. Rolland, S. T. Konenkov, I. E. Repin, A. V. Lunacharsky, N. K. Krupskaya, etc.).

O. Rodin spoke about his works like this: "This is strong, very strong", and noted that he sees they have incredible power and expression. A. M. Gorky called them talented and vital, touching the heart. L. N. Tolstoy noted the great power of expressiveness in sculptors of Zhukov.

I. N. Zhukov promoted the idea of a children's communist movement in sculpture. Zhukov's sculptural work was widely known at that time. He created about a thousand works, and his works invariably found a grateful response.

His sculptures were also portraits and genre scenes, full of love for people and irony. At the same time, in them he sometimes also ridiculed human vices and vulgarity. During the war years, Zhukov, while being evacuated, began to make original smoking pipes out of clay in the form of funny faces or caricature images of fascists. The sculptor sent these tubes to the front and received letters of gratitude from the fighters in response. The soldiers noted that Zhukov's cheerful pipes raised morale and made them want to beat the enemy even harder.

In 1925-1931, I. N. Zhukov was a geography teacher in the senior groups (classes) of schools No. 15, 40, 41 of the Bauman district in Moscow, and the school of the Institute of Physical Education.

Teacher Elsa Yanovna Grobin, who then worked at Moscow school No. 355, and knew I. N. Zhukov intimately, left her memories of the innovative teacher: "He had his own interesting teaching methods, he taught students to discover something new on their own and organized fascinating correspondence trips around the world map. Innokenty Nikolaevich prepared many interesting visual aids on the subject. He naturally, easily, enthusiastically interested students in his subject, conducted interesting extracurricular activities. In his daily work, he taught the ability to observe, understand, instilled a love for nature, developed an inquisitive mind, the ability to independently delve into and learn the beauty and secrets of nature. I. N. Zhukov knew child psychology perfectly well, loved children, so he was always surrounded by them" [28, p. 11].

Zhukov conducted "Geographical battles" between classes. Each student in one class had to write 3 questions. The question papers were distributed in another classroom. The guys not only picked up answers, but also in turn came up with their own questions for the opponent" [21, p. 18].

He was tireless in his work, and the most important thing was that he had his own original teaching methods. Zhukov taught children how to work independently, organized exciting trips around the world map.

He conducted geography games, contests, quizzes and geographical battles between classes. At one of the conferences of educators in 1928, I. N. Zhukov drew the attention of teachers to intra- and inter-school competition, which, in his opinion, became a powerful method in educational work, and created students' interest in its results. In his pedagogical experiments, Zhukov used competition as a new method of work.

In 1933, he sent to the city department of education a rationalization proposal to launch a mobile children's journal in the apartments of residential buildings, which was a sketchbook, the first page of which was designed by Zhukov, and provided with an itinerary and a preface about the desired content of it. He assigned two pages to each apartment. The journal aroused great interest among children, and all its pages were filled with their drawings and literary experiences.

He used the method of traveling journals later, conducting campaigning work before the elections to the Soviets. He suggested using such "traveling" journals as a literary form that would serve and unite several detachments or schools.

CONCLUSION

I. N. Zhukov advocated a system "cleansed" of political and ideological layers. He tried to combine the "new ideological policy" with the ideas of chivalry, and many things worked out at the level of a specific group of children. His ideas were, in general, in demand during his lifetime, but they remain so to this day.

Now, when Russian society is in search of axiological ideological guidelines that could be used in the education of the younger generation, an appeal to the experience of I. N. Zhukov seems more than timely and justified.

He suggested the name pioneers, which immediately stuck for many years. It also seems valuable in Zhukov's legacy that his ideas found adequate methodological elaboration, i.e. they were quite feasible in ordinary school practice.

The circumstances of the wonderful scoutmaster's life, the breadth of his interests, the inexhaustible desire to constantly improve his work, – all this serves as a wonderful example for the modern generation of Russian teachers.

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Помелов В. Б.: концептуализация, методология,
создание рукописи и ее редактирование,
руководство исследованием

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Vladimir B. Pomelov: Conceptualization, Methodology,
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Автор заявляет об отсутствии конфликта интересов

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The author declared no conflicts of interest